

ROLL OF AGANFOR POWDER AND DIETARY PLAN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF AMLAPITTA: CASE REPORT

Dr. Manoj Kumar Sharma^{1*}, Dr. Venu Sharma², Dr. Chhavi Jadoun³

*¹B.A.M.S. Rashtriya Guru, Ayurvedacharya, Founder of Ayurvedic Neuro Therapy, Elanza Apartment, Shreenathpuram Sector- C, Kota (Raj.) India.

²B.A.M.S., M.O., Daudayal Joshi Ayurvedic Chikitsalay, Talwandi, Kota, Rajasthan, India.

³B.A.M.S., Kota (Rajasthan), India.

Article Received on 31 October 2025,
Article Revised on 20 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17735725>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Manoj Kumar Sharma

B.A.M.S. Rashtriya Guru,
Ayurvedacharya, Founder of
Ayurvedic Neuro Therapy, Elanza
Apartment, Shreenathpuram Sector- C,
Kota (Raj.) India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Manoj Kumar Sharma^{1*}, Dr. Venu Sharma², Dr. Chhavi Jadoun³. (2025). ROLL OF AGANFOR POWDER AND DIETARY PLAN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF AMLAPITTA: CASE REPORT. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 891–896.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Gastric issues, particularly indigestion or dyspepsia, rank among the most common gastrointestinal disorders. Indigestion is not a disease, as it is a group of symptoms attributed to poorly digested food. Symptoms are typically described as upper abdominal pain and discomfort, sometimes with nausea, belching, and bloating, etc. The condition is connected to factors related to unhealthy habits in diet and lifestyle including overeating, erratic timing of meals, alcohol consumption, stress and smoking, etc. In general, gastric issues like indigestion are common but typically ignored. From an Ayurvedic perspective, indigestion or hyperacidity is called *Amlapitta*. This is a common *Pitta*-related digestive disorder primarily caused by excess secretion and/or vitiation of *Pitta dosha* in the *Amashaya* and *Pakwashaya*. Ayurveda suggested many therapeutic options for managing this condition and one such approach is traditional Ayurvedic formulation. This article presented a case report of successful management of *Amlapitta* through a traditional formulation *Aganfor* powder.

KEYWORDS: *Indigestion, Dyspepsia, Gastritis, Amlapitta, Pitta dosha.*

INTRODUCTION

Gastric problems are common digestive disorders of all ages. Indigestion (dyspepsia) is one of the most common disorders of digestion. Indigestion is defined as impaired digestion and presents with an upper abdominal discomfort, nausea, belching, heaviness and bloating, etc. Indigestion may occur due to the unhealthy dietary practices, eating out of time, eating spicy and oily foods, and certain lifestyle practices like smoking and alcohol consumption, etc.

In Ayurveda *Amlapitta* indicates the predominance of *Amla* and *Tikta* qualities associated with the disorder. *Amlapitta* is classified as a *Jatharagni* disorder or dysfunction due primarily to *Pitta dosha* vitiation and impaired *Agni*. The causes (*Nidana*) of *Amlapitta* are as follows:

- ✓ *Viruddha Ahara*
- ✓ *Aniyamita Ahara-Vihara*
- ✓ *Divaswapna*
- ✓ *Ratri Jagarana*
- ✓ *Amlia Padartha*
- ✓ *Dinacharya Parivartan*
- ✓ *Ritucharya Asatmya*
- ✓ *Madyapana*
- ✓ *Vegadharana*

Type of *Amlapitta* Based on *Dosha* predominance

- ✓ *Vataja Amlapitta*
- ✓ *Kaphaja Amlapitta*
- ✓ *Vata-Kaphaja Amlapitta*

Type of *Amlapitta* Based on the direction of movement (*Gati*)

- ✓ *Urdhvagata* (upward movement; leading to belching, nausea, vomiting)
- ✓ *Adhogata* (downward movement; leading to burning and discomfort in the abdomen)

Symptoms (*Lakshana*)

- ✓ Sour belching (*Khatti Dakkar*)
- ✓ Burning sensation in the chest (*Hridayadaha*)
- ✓ Heaviness in the food pipe (*Aharanala Gaurava*)
- ✓ Abdominal pain (*Udara Shoola*)

- ✓ Loss of appetite (*Aruchi*)

Amlapitta is directly involved with the imbalance of *Jatharagni*. This disorder can be treated by diet modification, lifestyle amendments and using Ayurveda medicines. *Amlapitta* can be managed effectively by using *Basti* therapy, hot cupping method in which mild suction is created by heating cups placed on the body, this treatment increases circulation, remove toxins and pacify *Pitta* and *Kapha doshas*. Herbal medicine like *Aganfor* powder may also be utilized for this type of conditions specifically caused by vitiation of *Pitta* and *Kapha doshas*.

Aganfor Powder

Aganfor powder is a classical Ayurvedic herbal formulation established for good therapeutic effects in diseases provoked by a vitiated *Pitta* and *Kapha doshas*, such as *Amlapitta* and other gut disorders. This formulation is primarily indicated for *Amlapitta* due to the presence of ingredients like *Avipattikar Churna*, *Mulethi*, *Amla* and Sodium Bicarbonate, etc. This formulation helps to calm *Pitta dosha*; improves *Agni* and relieves excessive acidity. Unlike antacids from modern medicine, which merely neutralize stomach acid, *Aganfor* powder takes on the root cause by restoring digestion and metabolism. The pharmacological effects of each ingredient are as follows:

- ✚ *Avipattikar Churna* imparts *Pitta Shamaka*, *Deepana*, *Pachana* and *Mridu Virechana* effects.
- ✚ *Mulethi* offers anti-ulcer, anti-inflammatory and demulcent effects; protects the gastric mucosa.
- ✚ *Amla* acts as *Rasayana*, gives antioxidant and *Pitta Shamaka* effects; also protect tissues.
- ✚ Sodium Bicarbonate acts as an antacid; neutralizes gastric acid and providing instant relief from acidity.

Aganfor powder mainly recommended for *Amlapitta*, gastritis, acid reflux, heartburn, *Vibandha*, *Adhmana* and loss of appetite. Ayurvedic properties of each ingredient of *Aganfor* powder are depicted in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Ayurvedic Properties of Ingredients of Aganfor powder.

Ingredients of formulation	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka
<i>Avipattikar Churna</i>	<i>Madhura, Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
<i>Mulethi</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
<i>Amla</i>	<i>Amla, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
<i>Sodium Bicarbonate</i>	<i>Kshara</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>

CASE REPORT

A 30-year-old male patient presented with complaints of burning sensation in the epigastric region, accompanied by nausea and a feeling of heaviness in the abdomen. Based on the clinical features, the condition was diagnosed as *Amlapitta*.

TREATMENT PLAN

- ✓ *Aganfor* powder: 3 g at bedtime with lukewarm water
- ✓ *Kamdudha Ras*: 125 mg twice daily with milk

Advised Ayurvedic Neuro Therapy

- ✓ Hot Cupping Therapy
- ✓ Vacuum Therapy
- ✓ Abdominal Therapy
- ✓ Follow prescribed diet chart

Pathya (Recommended Wholesome Diet)

- ✓ Light and cooling food
- ✓ *Moong dal* (green gram)
- ✓ *Takra* (buttermilk)

Apathya (To Be Avoided)

- ✓ Oily and spicy food
- ✓ Late-night waking
- ✓ Excessive tea consumption

Follow-Up Period

- ✓ After 15 Days of Treatment

RESULT AND OBSERVATIONS

The burning sensation was reduced by nearly 80%, and the patient experienced a noticeable improvement in appetite. Nausea was completely absent, and the patient reported significant relief along with an overall sense of well-being as mentioned in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Comparative observation of therapy on assessment parameters.

Symptoms	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Sour Belching	Frequent, severe	Gradually reduced
Burning Sensation	High intensity (chest & throat)	Intensity decreased
Digestion	Improper, heaviness after meals	Proper digestion, feeling of lightness
Appetite	Reduced	Increased
Abdominal Pain	Present, moderate	Gradually reduced
Gas & Heaviness	Frequent	Significantly reduced
<i>Ama</i> (Toxin Formation)	Present due to improper digestion	Controlled due to balanced digestion
Sleep	Disturbed due to acidity	Improved, sound sleep
Recurrence of Acidity	Frequent	Considerably reduced
Overall Well-being	Distressed and uncomfortable	Healthy, cheerful, and satisfied

DISCUSSION

After beginning with *Aganfor* powder and Ayurvedic Neuro therapy, the patient had a gradual decrease in sour belching and a marked reduction in burning sensations. There was significant improvement in digestion, and the patient reported an increase in appetite and reduced abdominal pain. Gas, heaviness, and indigestion had reduced significantly with a balance of *Agni*. *Ama* was not formed, resulting in improved digestion and absorption. Improved digestion also results in quality sleep and there was considerably reduction in acidity episodes.

Probable Mechanism of Action

Avipattikar Churna and *Amla* pacify aggravated, decreases *Pitta dosha* to reduces acidity and burning sensations. *Mulethi* improves *Agni*, imparts soothing effects by covering stomach lining while preventing ulcer formation. *Mridu Virechana* renders a systematic elimination of toxins while maintaining digestive equilibrium. Sodium bicarbonate relieves hyperacidity conditions immediately by neutralizing excessive stomach acid. *Aganfor Churna* is a reliable and efficacious remedy in Ayurveda, which curbs acidity, gastritis, and indigestion. It imparts *Pitta Shamana*, *Deepana-Pachana* & *Mridu Virechana* effects, also improves digestion and detoxifies body, thus support health of the gastrointestinal tract.

CONCLUSION

Aganfor Churna is considered beneficial for treating *Amlapitta*, because it acts on both the symptoms as well as the root cause of the problem. While most conventional medicines aim to neutralize the acid and suppress its acid secretion activity, *Aganfor Churna* corrects *Agni-dushti*, the primary cause of *Amlapitta*. The ingredients of *Aganfor Churna* works

synergistically together in pacifying excessive *Pitta*, improves digestion, protecting gastric mucosa and eliminates toxins. Therefore, *Aganfor* not only diminishes the burning sensation, acidity and bloating, but it also restores healthy digestion to enable long term health benefit without side effects.

REFERENCES

1. Madhava Nidana. *Annaroga Adhikara (Chapter 10)*. Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi.
2. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. *Amlapitta Adhikara (Chapter 38)*. Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhawan, Varanasi.
3. Charaka Samhita. *Chikitsa Sthana 1/30*. Edited by Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi.
4. Sushruta Samhita. *Sutra Sthana 38*. Edited by Kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi.
5. Charaka Samhita. *Sutra Sthana 27*. Edited by Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi.
6. Sushruta Samhita. *Sutra Sthana 46*. Edited by Kaviraj Ambikadatta Shastri, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi.